

WP3 Recruitment Protocol

Expert interviews with Swiss and Bulgarian retailers on the listing of NGT (CRISPR-edited) products

Project: Addressing the Genetically Modified Agricultural Products Conundrum — A Holistic Approach
SciEx IZSF-0_235780 (Swiss National Science Foundation) • Sofia University «St. Kliment Ohridski»
and Agroscope • Version 1, 01.07.2026

Summary

This protocol governs the recruitment of senior decision-makers in Swiss and Bulgarian retail organisations into the WP3 component of the SciEx CH–BG project on the acceptance and listing of New Genomic Techniques (NGTs, including CRISPR-edited products) in the food trade. It sets out the sampling frame and the full Switzerland and Bulgaria sampling matrices, inclusion and exclusion criteria, the staged recruitment and snowball procedure, substitution rules, contact and consent procedures, data-protection arrangements, and German and Bulgarian invitation templates. It supports the open-archive deposit of the project’s procedural record and is intended to permit independent replication and audit. The companion Methodology Note states the pre-specified propositions, the saturation criterion and the analytic strategy.

1. Sample frame and matrices

The target population in each country is the set of senior individuals with substantive influence over strategic listing decisions for new, regulatorily sensitive product categories in retail. The population is small, so sampling is purposive rather than probabilistic. The unit of analysis is the organisation, not the individual store or branch.

The sampling frame is constructed from publicly verifiable sources. The full priority-ranked matrices — fourteen target organisations for Switzerland and twelve for Bulgaria — are set out in Tables 1 and 2 below.

Table 1. Switzerland sampling matrix (target 12–14 interviews; interview language German or English, French contingent for Romandie).

#	Organisation	Structure	Segment	Target role	Region	Priority
1	Coop Genossenschaft (Basel)	Single national cooperative	Mainstream retail	Director Category Management Food	National	A
2	Migros Federation (MGB, Zürich)	Cooperative federation HQ; Migros Supermarkt AG centralises buying since 2024	Mainstream retail	Director Category Management Fresh, or Generaldirektion member for Sortiment	National	A
3	Migros Aare (Schönbühl BE)	Regional cooperative, separate legal entity, largest of the ten	Mainstream retail	Geschäftsleiter, or Head of Fresh	Bern, Solothurn, Aargau (DE-CH)	A
4	Migros Ostschweiz (Gossau SG)	Regional cooperative, agricultural east	Mainstream retail	Geschäftsleiter, or Head of Fresh	SG, TG, AR, AI, GL, SH, GR (DE-CH)	A
5	Migros Vaud (Ecublens)	Regional cooperative, largest in Romandie	Mainstream retail	Directeur, or Head of Fresh	Vaud (FR-CH)	A (FR feasibility)
6	Denner AG (Zürich)	Joint-stock company, wholly owned by MGB	Domestic discount	Head of Buying, or Category Manager Fresh	National	A
7	fenaco / Volg (Bern, Winterthur)	Agricultural cooperative federation owned by farmers via 137 Landi cooperatives	Rural retail and agribusiness	Member of Geschäftsleitung Detailhandel, or Head of Volg Sortiment	National (rural)	A
8	Transgourmet Schweiz (Basel)	Joint-stock company, Coop subsidiary	Wholesale (B2B)	Category Manager Fresh, or Director Procurement	National	A
9	Lidl Schweiz AG (Weinfelden TG)	Joint-stock company, Schwarz Group subsidiary	Foreign discount	Director Buying, or Category Manager	National	A

#	Organisation	Structure	Segment	Target role	Region	Priority
10	Aldi Suisse AG (Schwarzenbach SG)	Joint-stock company, Aldi Süd subsidiary	Foreign discount	Director Buying, or Category Buying Manager	National	B
11	Landi Schweiz AG (Winterthur)	Cooperative subsidiary of fenaco	Farm-input retail with food	Geschäftsleitung member	National (rural)	B
12	Manor Food (Basel)	Premium food division of privately held Maus Frères	Premium urban	Head of Manor Food merchandising	National (urban)	B
13	Pistor AG (Rothenburg LU)	Cooperative of business members (bakeries, confectioneries, gastronomy)	Wholesale (B2B)	Head of Buying, or Category Manager	National	C
14	Migrolino AG, or Coop Pronto	Convenience subsidiaries of Migros and Coop	Convenience retail	Head of Buying	National	C

Migros Basel, Zürich, Genève, Neuchâtel-Fribourg, Luzern and Valais serve as alternates within the same priority tier in case of refusal. Bio Suisse is a possible additional contact for the explicitly anti-NGT position. The three Swiss players (Coop, Migros, fenaco) must be represented. Further participants can be added.

Table 2. Bulgaria sampling matrix (target 10–12 interviews; interview language Bulgarian; coordinated by Prof. Petyo Bonev).

#	Organisation	Structure	Segment	Target role	Region	Priority
1	Kaufland Bulgaria (Sofia)	Subsidiary of Schwarz Group	Foreign hypermarket	Head of Corporate Communications and buying contact	National	A
2	Lidl Bulgaria (Sofia)	Subsidiary of Schwarz Group	Foreign discount	Head of Corporate Communications	National	A
3	BILLA Bulgaria (Sofia)	Subsidiary of REWE Group	Foreign supermarket	Corporate Communications and Strategy	National (urban)	A
4	Fantastico (Sofia, VAN Holding)	Privately held domestic family business	Domestic supermarket	Owner, or Commercial Director	Sofia metropolitan	A (only large BG-owned chain)
5	T MARKET (Plovdiv, Maxima Bulgaria)	Subsidiary of Latvian Maxima Group	Foreign supermarket with former domestic identity	Country Manager Bulgaria	National	A
6	Lexy (Plovdiv)	Privately held domestic family business	Premium domestic supermarket	Owner	Plovdiv	A (parallel to Manor CH)
7	METRO Cash and Carry Bulgaria	Joint-stock company, foreign-owned	Wholesale (B2B)	Head of Communications and Sustainability	National (multi-city)	A
8	CBA Bulgaria	Domestic cooperative network of 25 chains	Domestic cooperative supermarket	Management	Multi-city, 40+ towns	B
9	SVA / Burleks	Domestic regional chain	Domestic regional supermarket	Management	NE Bulgaria (Varna, Russe, V. Tarnovo, Dobrich, Gabrovo)	B
10	Bolero Supermarkets (Burgas)	Domestic regional, CBA franchise	Domestic regional supermarket	Owner	SE Bulgaria (Burgas, Stara Zagora)	B
11	Minimart	Domestic chain	Convenience	Management	Multi-city (Sofia, Stara Zagora, Pernik, Burgas)	C
12	Modern Trade Association (MTA)	Industry umbrella	Backup channel	Executive Director	National	C

The Bulgarian sample must include at least one foreign discounter, one foreign supermarket and one large domestic chain. Further participants can be added.

The two matrices are designed for direct between-country comparison within ownership types (for example, Lidl Bulgaria with Lidl Schweiz; METRO Bulgaria with Transgourmet on the

business-to-business axis; Fantastico and Lexy with Manor Food on the privately held domestic axis).

2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion

- A strategic role in category management, buying, or executive leadership of a retail organisation operating in Switzerland or Bulgaria (executive board / Geschäftsleitung; director of buying or category management; senior category manager for fresh produce, fruit and vegetables, dairy, or meat).
- At least three years of experience in the current organisation or in a relevant prior position.
- Capacity to speak to decisions concerning new, regulatorily sensitive product categories.
- Written informed consent (and consent to audio recording, or, as a fallback, to contemporaneous note-taking).

Exclusion

- Persons in purely operational roles (store managers without category responsibility).
- Persons in Public Affairs or Communications roles, whose function is to articulate the organisation's external voice rather than the internal logic of decisions.
- Persons with whom a direct commercial contract exists in the project, to avoid conflicts of interest.

3. Recruitment stages

Recruitment proceeds in three stages, beginning in the second week of July 2026.

- **Stage 1 — institutional approach (from the second week of July 2026).**
- **Stage 2 — network-based introductions (July 2026, in parallel).**
- **Stage 3 — snowball sampling (August 2026 onwards).**

4. Substitution rules

If the initially proposed person declines, the following hierarchy applies:

- First, request a substitute from the same organisation with a comparable role, preserving the organisational representation.
- Second, if the organisation declines as a whole, substitute with a comparable organisation in the same segment and region.
- Third, if a whole segment proves systematically inaccessible, document this in the limitations section and compensate through deeper desk research on publicly available strategic documents.

5. Contact procedure

5.1 First contact

- Email (or formal letter) is the primary first-contact mode.
- Attached: the one-page project description (Annex 1, available in German, English and Bulgarian).
- The interview guide is offered in advance on request.
- Where a contact has been provided through a referral, the introductory message may name the referring person, conditional on their prior consent.

5.2 Follow-up

- No response within 10 working days: a follow-up email.
- No response within 20 working days: a single follow-up.
- No response within 30 working days: recorded as 'no response' and removed from active recruitment.

5.3 Scheduling

- Three to four time slots offered per response, across a two-week window.
- Format at the respondent's choice: videoconference (Microsoft Teams or Zoom) or in person at their workplace.
- A confirmation email is sent two days before the interview.

6. Documentation and tracking

All recruitment activity is logged in a single Recruitment Tracker (Excel), with one row per contact and timestamped status updates (name, organisation, role, segment, source/referrer, dates contacted, outcome, reason for non-completion). In line with the Data Management Plan submitted to the Swiss National Science Foundation, the Tracker is held on the secured Agroscope servers; it contains personal data and is NOT archived publicly. Prior to the first interview, the procedural artefacts that contain no personal data are pre-registered on a FAIR-aligned, non-profit open-research repository (Zenodo or equivalent) under a CC BY 4.0 licence.

7. Informed consent procedure

- The written consent form (German/English for the Swiss arm; Bulgarian for the Bulgarian arm) is sent ahead of the interview together with the interview questions.
- Key consent points are reviewed orally at the start of the interview.
- Signed consent is obtained before recording starts. If recording consent is declined, contemporaneous notes are taken instead.
- Anonymisation operates at two levels: personal anonymisation is the default; organisational anonymisation is offered as an option, with attribution at organisational level only against the participant's explicit written consent.
- The participant may withdraw at any point without consequence; deletion of their contribution is honoured within thirty (30) days of a written request, subject to the limits of any analyses already published.

8. Post-interview procedure and data protection

- Within 24 hours: interview audio uploaded to the encrypted institutional server; field notes typed up.
- Within 7 days: a thank-you email is sent to the interviewee.
- Within 14 days: transcription completed; transcript pseudonymised.

Applicable law and roles. The revised Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection (revFADP / nDSG, in force since 01.09.2023) governs Swiss-side processing; the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act (ЗЗЛД) govern the Bulgarian arm. The lawful basis for organisational contact data is legitimate interest (GDPR Art. 6(1)(f)), drawn exclusively from public sources; the lawful basis for interview content is explicit informed consent (GDPR Art. 6(1)(a)). The hosting institution and data controller is Agroscope (Federal Research Institute for Agriculture, Tänikon 1, CH-8356 Ettenhausen). Storage is on secured Agroscope servers, encrypted at rest, with retention of at least ten years; transcripts are pseudonymised; only anonymised, organisation-level artefacts are ever deposited openly, and the Recruitment Tracker is never published.

Ethics approval. Two independent Bulgarian ethics committees have approved the study, with remit covering both country arms: the Ethics Committee of Sofia University «Sv. Kliment

Ohridski» (ref. № 93-K-72/17.04.2026; chair Prof. Dr Romyana Marinova-Hristidi) and the Ethics Committee of the Bulgarian Sociological Association (session of 15.05.2026; chair Prof. Dr Tatyana Kotseva). The Swiss leg follows the Agroscope research-integrity and ethics framework.

9. Invitation email template

Български

Относно: **Покана за интервю по научен проект – нови геномни техники – Фокус: Мнението на търговците на дребно**

Уважаема г-жо / Уважаеми г-н [фамилия],

Свързвам се с Вас във връзка с научноизследователски проект в Agroscope (Швейцария), който анализира социални аспекти свързани с модерните технологии за растителна селекция (по-специално CRISPR-базирани нови геномни техники, НГТ) в търговията на дребно в Швейцария (проект SciEx, IZSF-0_235780).

Ще Ви бъдем много благодарни за Вашето участие и Вашия принос – еднократен разговор с представител на **ръководно ниво** от Вашата организация, за предпочитане от направление „категориен мениджмънт“, „асортимент“ или „доставки“, с 2 и повече години опит по специалността. С Вашето участие Вие пряко допринасяте за по-доброто разбиране на позицията и опита на търговския сектор по отношение на новите геномни техники, както и за изграждането на научно обоснован диалог между изследователи, регулаторни органи и бранша в България.

Рамка на интервюто

- **Продължителност:** около 60 минути
- **Език:** български
- **Формат:** по Ваш избор — видеоконференция (Microsoft Teams или Zoom)
- **Период:** при първа възможност през периода юли–август, поради ограничената продължителност на проекта. Ако това не е възможно, но бихте желали да участвате, ще се съобразим с Вашия график и ще се радваме да разговаряме с Вас при първа възможност (моля, уточнете кога).
- **Подготовка:** ще Ви изпратим въпросника предварително

Прилагам едностранично описание на проекта с допълнителна информация. На разположение съм за въпроси и за уговаряне на удобен за Вас час.

Ще Ви бъда благодарна за Вашия отговор.

С уважение,

д-р Ива Михайлова — Софийски университет, България и Agroscope, Швейцария
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Приложение: Описание на проекта (1 страница)

Deutsch

Betreff: Einladung zum Interview für ein Forschungsprojekt – Neue genomische Techniken – Fokus: Sicht der Einzelhändler

Sehr geehrte Frau / Sehr geehrter Herr [Nachname],

ich wende mich an Sie im Zusammenhang mit einem Forschungsprojekt von Agroscope (Schweiz), das sich mit sozialen Aspekten moderner Pflanzenzüchtungstechnologien (insbesondere CRISPR-basierten neuen genomischen Techniken, NGT) im Schweizer Einzelhandel befasst (SciEx-Projekt, IZSF-0_235780).

Wir wären Ihnen sehr dankbar für Ihre Teilnahme und Ihren Beitrag – ein einmaliges Gespräch mit einer **Führungskraft** aus Ihrem Unternehmen, vorzugsweise aus den Bereichen Category Management, Sortiment oder Beschaffung, mit mindestens 2 Jahren Erfahrung im Fachgebiet. Mit Ihrer Teilnahme tragen Sie direkt zu einem besseren Verständnis der Position und Erfahrung des Handelssektors gegenüber neuen genomischen Techniken bei, sowie zum Aufbau eines wissenschaftlich fundierten Dialogs zwischen Forschenden, Regulierungsbehörden und der Branche in Bulgarien.

Rahmen des Interviews

- **Dauer:** ca. 60 Minuten
- **Sprache:** Bulgarisch
- **Format:** nach Ihrer Wahl — Videokonferenz (Microsoft Teams oder Zoom)
- **Zeitraum:** möglichst bald im Zeitraum Juli–August, aufgrund der begrenzten Projektlaufzeit. Sollte dies nicht möglich sein, Sie aber gerne teilnehmen möchten, richten wir uns nach Ihrem Zeitplan und freuen uns, so bald wie möglich mit Ihnen zu sprechen (bitte teilen Sie uns einen passenden Zeitpunkt mit).
- **Vorbereitung:** gerne senden wir Ihnen den Fragebogen vorab zu

Im Anhang finden Sie eine einseitige Projektbeschreibung mit weiteren Informationen. Für Fragen und zur Terminvereinbarung stehe ich Ihnen gerne zur Verfügung.

Ich freue mich auf Ihre Antwort.

Mit freundlichen Grüßen,

Dr. Iva Mihaylova — Universität Sofia, Bulgarien und Agroscope, Schweiz

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Anhang: Projektbeschreibung (1 Seite)

English

Subject: Invitation to Interview for a Research Project – New Genomic Techniques – Focus: Retailers' Perspective

Dear Mr./Ms. [Last Name],

I am writing to you regarding a research project at Agroscope (Switzerland) that examines the social aspects of modern plant breeding technologies (in particular CRISPR-based new genomic techniques, NGTs) in Swiss retail (SciEx project, IZSF-0_235780).

We would be very grateful for your participation and contribution — a one-time conversation with a senior representative from your organization, preferably from category management, assortment planning, or procurement, with 2 or more years of experience in the field. Through your participation, you directly contribute to a better understanding of the retail sector's position and experience regarding new genomic techniques, as well as to building a scientifically grounded dialogue between researchers, regulators, and the industry in Bulgaria.

Interview framework

- **Duration:** approximately 60 minutes
- **Language:** Bulgarian
- **Format:** your choice — video conference (Microsoft Teams or Zoom)
- **Timeframe:** as soon as possible during July–August, due to the project's limited timeline. If this is not possible but you would still like to participate, we will accommodate your schedule and look forward to speaking with you at the earliest opportunity (please let us know a suitable time).
- **Preparation:** if desired, we will send you the questionnaire in advance

Attached is a one-page project description with additional information. I am available for any questions and to arrange a convenient time.

I look forward to your response.

Sincerely,

Dr. Iva Mihaylova — Sofia University, Bulgaria and Agroscope, Switzerland
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iva.mihaylova@agroscope.admin.ch

Attachment: Project description (1 page)

Български

Проблематиката на генетично модифицираните селскостопански продукти: Цялостен подход

Номер на проекта: SciEx IZSF-0_235780

Финансиране: програма SciEx

Продължителност: февруари 2026 – юли 2027

Изпълняваща институция: Софийски университет, България и Agroscope, Швейцария

Контекст

Европейският съюз обсъжда основно преработване на регулацията на новите геномни техники (НГТ), по-специално CRISPR-базираната растителна селекция. През следващите години Швейцария ще определи собствената си регулаторна рамка. Предпоставка за обосноваване регулаторен дебат е знанието за начина, по който основните участници по цялата верига на добавена стойност оценяват приемането на такива продукти.

Изследователски цели

Проектът изследва, в структурно сравнение между Швейцария и България, как различните групи участници оценяват приемането на CRISPR-базирани селскостопански продукти и кои фактори формират тяхната позиция.

Три работни пакета

- **РП1 Потребители:** представително проучване на населението на двете държави относно знания, отношение и готовност за плащане
- **РП2 Земеделие:** интервюта с организации от агро-хранителния бранш относно решенията за отглеждане и производство
- **РП3 Търговия на дребно:** експертни интервюта с вземащи решения в търговски дружества на дребно (настоящото изследване)

Ръководство на проекта

Д-р Ива Михайлова и проф. д-р Петьо Бонев (Agroscope) съвместно ръководят проекта.

Защита на данните и научна етика

Проектът разполага с одобрение от Комисията по етика (независим орган, който защитава правата и интересите на участниците в научни изследвания). Гарантираме спазването на следните принципи: информирано съгласие; пълна анонимност и поверителност; правото да откажете участие или да прекратите участието си във всеки момент без последствия; защита на данните съгласно действащото законодателство на съответната държава; сигурно съхранение в защитени с парола файлове на сървърите на Agroscope; възможност за изтриване на Вашия принос при желание.

Контакт

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Deutsch

Die Problematik gentechnisch veränderter Agrarprodukte: Ein ganzheitlicher Ansatz

Projektnummer: SciEx IZSF-0_235780

Förderung: Schweizerischer Nationalfonds (SNF), SciEx-Programm

Laufzeit: Februar 2026 bis Juli 2027

Durchführende Institution: Universität Sofia, Bulgarien und Agroscope, Schweiz

Hintergrund

Die Europäische Union diskutiert eine grundlegende Neufassung der Regulierung neuer genomischer Techniken (NGT), insbesondere CRISPR-basierter Pflanzenzüchtung. Die Schweiz wird in den kommenden Jahren ihre eigenen regulatorischen Weichen stellen. Voraussetzung für eine fundierte regulatorische Debatte ist Wissen darüber, wie zentrale Akteure entlang der Wertschöpfungskette die Aufnahme solcher Produkte einschätzen.

Forschungsziele

Das Projekt untersucht in einem strukturellen Vergleich Schweiz und Bulgarien, wie unterschiedliche Akteursgruppen die Akzeptanz CRISPR-basierter Agrarprodukte einschätzen und welche Faktoren ihre Haltung prägen.

Drei Arbeitspakete

- **WP1 Konsumentinnen und Konsumenten:** repräsentative Befragung der Bevölkerung beider Länder zu Wissen, Einstellungen und Zahlungsbereitschaft
- **WP2 Landwirtschaft:** Interviews mit Organisationen der Agrar- und Lebensmittelbranche zu Anbau- und Produktionsentscheidungen
- **WP3 Detailhandel:** Experteninterviews mit Entscheidungsträgerinnen und Entscheidungsträgern in Detailhandelsunternehmen (das vorliegende Anliegen)

Projektleitung

Dr. Iva Mihaylova und Prof. Dr. Petyo Bonev (Agroscope) leiten das Projekt gemeinsam.

Datenschutz und Forschungsethik

Das Projekt verfügt über die Genehmigung der Ethikkommission (eines unabhängigen Gremiums, das die Rechte und Interessen der Teilnehmenden an wissenschaftlichen Studien schützt). Wir gewährleisten die Einhaltung der folgenden Grundsätze: informierte Einwilligung; vollständige Anonymität und Vertraulichkeit; das Recht, die Teilnahme jederzeit ohne Folgen zu verweigern oder abubrechen; Datenschutz gemäss der geltenden Gesetzgebung des jeweiligen Landes; sichere Aufbewahrung in passwortgeschützten Dateien auf den Servern von Agroscope; die Möglichkeit, Ihren Beitrag auf Wunsch löschen zu lassen.

Kontakt

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English

Addressing the Genetically Modified Agricultural Products Conundrum — A Holistic Approach

Project number: SciEx IZSF-0_235780

Funding: Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), SciEx Programme

Duration: February 2026 to July 2027

Implementing institution: Sofia University, Bulgaria and Agroscope, Switzerland

Background

The European Union is discussing a fundamental revision of the regulation of new genomic techniques (NGTs), particularly CRISPR-based plant breeding. In the coming years, Switzerland will set its own regulatory course. A well-founded regulatory debate requires knowledge of how key actors along the value chain assess the acceptance of such products.

Research objectives

Through a structural comparison of Switzerland and Bulgaria, the project examines how different groups of actors assess the acceptance of CRISPR-based agricultural products and which factors shape their attitudes.

Three work packages

- **WP1 Consumers:** representative survey of the population in both countries on knowledge, attitudes, and willingness to pay
- **WP2 Agriculture:** interviews with agri-food branch organisations on cultivation and production decisions
- **WP3 Retail:** expert interviews with decision-makers in retailers (the present study)

Project leadership

Dr. Iva Mihaylova and Prof. Dr. Petyo Bonev (Agroscope) jointly lead the project.

Data protection and research ethics

The project has approval from the Ethics Committee (an independent body that protects the rights and interests of participants in scientific studies). We ensure compliance with the following principles: informed consent; full anonymity and confidentiality; the right to decline or withdraw participation at any time without consequences; data protection in accordance with the applicable legislation of the respective country; secure storage in password-protected files on Agroscope's servers; the option to have your contribution deleted upon request.

Contact

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